

Relationship between water sources and diarrhea incidence in North Buton Regency

Jumakil * and Asnia Zainuddin

Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(01), 650–655

Publication history: Received on 27 November 2023; revised on 03 January 2024; accepted on 06 January 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.1.0036>

Abstract

Background: The condition of water sources in the unprotected category is classified as unsafe sanitation facilities. This is very risky for endangering the people who use it as a source of clean water for their daily needs. In North Buton Regency, based on monitoring, unprotected water sources are still found, both dug wells and springs which are used by the community to meet their clean water needs.

Method: quantitative analytical, with a cross sectional study design. This research was carried out using a household survey method using a questionnaire, as well as observationally using an observation sheet. The sample in this study was 3,640 households, this number was obtained from 91 villages, where each village was represented by 40 households selected using the simple random sampling method.

Result: The results of this study show that there is a significant relationship between the use of dug well water sources and the incidence of diarrhea based on statistical tests using the chi square test, obtaining a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$. There is a relationship between the use of spring water and the incidence of diarrhea in North Buton Regency with a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$.

Conclusion: There is a significant relationship between dug wells and spring water sources and the incidence of diarrhea in North Buton Regency.

Keywords: Clean Water; Diarrhea; Relationships; Water Sources

1. Introduction

Diarrhea is the second leading cause of death in children under five years old, and the cause of death for approximately 525,000 children every year. Diarrhea can last several days, and it can leave the body without the water and salt necessary for survival. In the past, for most people, severe dehydration and fluid loss were the main causes of death from diarrhea[1].

In Indonesia, it is estimated that there are around 200-400 cases of diarrhea per 1000 population every year, so it can be estimated that there are more than 60 million cases of diarrhea every year [2]. In Southeast Sulawesi Province, 34,195 cases of diarrhea were recorded, and in North Buton Regency there were 916 cases recorded in 2020 [3].

Many factors cause diarrhea, morbidity and death. One of the high levels is generally caused by contaminated water and food sources. In the world, 780 million individuals have limited access to adequate drinking water and 2.5 million have limited access to adequate sanitation [2]. Consumption of drinking water from improved sources reduces the incidence of water-borne diseases and the risk of death[4]. Drinking unsafe water is one of the main factors causing diarrhea in children[5][6][7]. Improving water quality can reduce the incidence of diarrhea[8].

* Corresponding author: Jumakil

The condition of water sources in the unprotected category is classified as unsafe sanitation facilities. This is very risky for endangering the people who use it as a source of clean water for their daily needs. In North Buton Regency, based on monitoring, unprotected water sources are still found, both dug wells and springs which are used by the community to meet their clean water needs.

Based on the study above, research was conducted with the aim of finding out the relationship between clean water sources used by the community to meet their daily needs and the incidence of diarrhea in North Buton Regency in 2022.

2. Material and methods

This type of research is quantitative analytical, with a cross sectional study design. This research was carried out using a household survey method using a questionnaire, as well as observation using an observation sheet. The survey was carried out with the aim of obtaining information about the water sources used by respondents for their daily needs, and observation sheets were used for direct observation/observation of the water sources used by respondents, namely the types of dug wells and springs. This research was carried out in North Buton Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2022. The sample in this study was 3,640 households, this number was obtained from 91 villages, where each village was represented by 40 households selected using the simple random sampling method. Respondents in this study were housewives aged 17-56 years. The research results obtained were then input using the Microsoft Excel application, and then analyzed using the SPSS version 20.0 application. Analysis of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable uses the chi square test.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Univariate Analysis

Based on the survey results and validation carried out with the results of observations at clean water source facilities, the distribution of respondents for each variable was obtained, namely dug wells and springs as independent variables, and the incidence of diarrhea as the dependent variable. From the validation results, the distribution of respondents was obtained as follows:

3.1.1. Facilities for digging wells

The dig wells referred to in this research are dug wells that are used by the community to meet their daily clean water needs. The distribution of respondents who use dug wells can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Who Use Dug Wells as a Source of Clean Water in North Buton Regency in 2022

Dig Well	n	%
Not Protected	392	10.77
Protected	3,248	89.23
Total	3,640	100.00

Resource: Primary data, 2022

Based on table 1 above, out of 3,640 respondents, the majority of respondents used protected dug wells, namely 3,248 (89.23%) respondents. However, there are still respondents who use unprotected dug wells for their daily needs, namely 392 (10.77%) respondents.

3.1.2. Springs

The springs referred to in this research are water that comes from springs that are used by the community to meet their daily clean water needs. The distribution of respondents using spring water is presented in table 2 below:

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents Who Use Springs as a Source of Clean Water in North Buton Regency in 2022

Spring	n	%
Not Protected	67	1.84
Protected	3,573	98.16
Total	3,640	100.00

Resource: Primary data, 2022

Table 2 above shows that of the 3,640 respondents, the majority used water that came from protected springs, namely 3,573 (98.16%) respondents. However, there are still respondents who use water from unprotected springs for their daily needs, namely 67 (1.84%) respondents.

3.1.3. Diarrhea incident

The incidence of diarrhea referred to in this study is diarrheal disease experienced by people in all age groups based on the history of the disease they have experienced and been diagnosed with diarrhea since the last 6 months. The distribution of diarrhea incidents among respondents is presented in table 3 below:

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents Who Have One or More Family Members Suffering from Diarrhea in North Buton Regency in 2022

Diarrhea incident	n	%
Diarrhea	621	17.06
Not Diarrhea	3,019	82.94
Total	3,640	100.00

Resource: Primary data, 2022

Table 3 above shows that of the 3,640 respondents, the majority of family members have never experienced diarrhea in the last 6 months, namely 3,019 (82.94%) respondents. However, there are still family members of respondents who have experienced diarrhea since the last 6 months, namely 621 (17.6%) respondents.

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

3.2.1. Relationship between the use of dug wells and the incidence of diarrhea

Based on the data obtained, an analysis was then carried out to determine the relationship between the use of dug wells and the incidence of diarrhea. The relationship between these two variables is presented in table 4 below:

Table 4 Relationship between the use of dug wells and the incidence of diarrhea in North Buton Regency in 2022

Dig Well	Diarrhea incident				Total		P Value
	Diarrhea		Not Diarrhea		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not Protected	94	23.98	298	76.02	392	100	0.000
Protected	527	16.23	2,721	83.77	3,248	100	
Total	621	17.06	3,019	82.94	3,640	100	

Resource: Results of Primary Data Analysis in 2022

Table 4 shows that 23.98% of the 392 respondents who used unprotected dug wells as a source of clean water for their daily needs had experienced diarrhea, while 76.02% of those who had never experienced diarrhea had experienced diarrhea. Then, of the 3,248 respondents who used protected dug wells, 16.23% of their family members had experienced diarrhea, while 83.77% had never experienced diarrhea. The results of statistical tests using the chi square

test obtained a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that there is a significant relationship between the use of dug well water sources and the incidence of diarrhea.

3.2.2. Relationship between the use of spring water and the incidence of diarrhea

Based on the data obtained, an analysis was then carried out to determine the relationship between the use of spring water and the incidence of diarrhea. The relationship between these two variables is presented in table 5 below:

Table 5 Relationship between Spring Water Use and Diarrhea Incidence in North Buton Regency in 2022

Springs	Diarrhea incident				Total		P Value
	Diarrhea		Not Diarrhea		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Not Protected	29	43.28	38	56.72	67	100	0.000
Protected	592	16.57	2,981	83.43	3,573	100	
Total	621	17.06	3,19	82.94	3,640	100	

Resource: Results of Primary Data Analysis in 2022

Table 5 shows that 43.28% of the 67 respondents who used unprotected springs as a source of clean water for their daily needs had experienced diarrhea, while 56.72% had never experienced diarrhea. Then, of the 3,573 respondents who used protected dug wells, 16.57% of their family members had experienced diarrhea, while 83.43% had never experienced diarrhea. The results of statistical tests using the chi square test obtained a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that there is a significant relationship between the use of spring water and the incidence of diarrhea.

Water is vital in human life [9], plants [10] and animals [11]. For daily needs, humans use the water sources around them. Most of the water sources closest to homes come from groundwater, so humans build water sources such as dug wells. Apart from that, people can also take advantage of springs which are usually far from their living environment. However, because of necessity, people try to obtain it.

The conditions of dug wells in North Buton Regency vary. Most of them are classified as protected, but there are still some that are not protected. These unprotected dug wells are partly because some have no well walls, no well rim, no watertight floor around them, and also do not have waste disposal channels. Apart from that, dug wells were still found with a distance of less than 10 meters from the latrine. Likewise with springs. Some people use protected springs, but there are still those who use unprotected springs. Unprotected springs do not have their own reservoir and the springs are not closed and do not have protection around them, making it easier for pollutants to enter the spring water source.

Water sources that will be consumed by the community must be kept clean. Water source pollution can come from the surrounding environment, so the water source facility must be protected from sources of pollution. Water for hygiene and sanitation purposes, water sources must be protected from sources of pollution, disease-carrying animals and vector breeding sites, and safe from possible contamination [12]. Unprotected water sources can be contaminated by bacteria, which can cause diarrhea. The use of unprotected water sources is related to the incidence of diarrhea experienced by the community [13].

Regular detection of bacteria in various water sources such as municipal water, water supply for businesses or homes, recreational waters, and so on is needed to identify and prevent potential health/environmental risks to ensure public health globally [14].

This research shows that there is a relationship between the use of dug wells and springs and the incidence of diarrhea. This happens because the majority of people who use unprotected water sources suffer from diarrhea, while the majority of people who do not have diarrhea use protected water sources. This research is in line with research conducted by Marini et al [15], Slamet Ifandi [16], and Italia et al [17].

Dug wells have the potential to be a source of transmission of diarrheal disease due to well water being contaminated by fecal coliforms. Shallow dug wells are more easily contaminated with fecal coliforms compared to deep dug wells [18]. Water can be related to the depth and type of well, its operation, maintenance and the presence of pollution sources in the vicinity such as latrines[19] and rubbish dumps[20][21].

Significant health consequences of consuming unsafe water include dysentery and other diarrheal diseases due to microbiological contaminants. Drinking water pollution continues to increase in urban areas due to demographic expansion, and puts many communities at risk[22]. The main cause of fecal contamination in this water source is thought to be anthropogenic. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate a policy aimed at managing and increasing resources[23].

4. Conclusion

There is a relationship between dug wells and spring water sources and the incidence of diarrhea in North Buton Regency, with a P value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Communities must pay more attention to the safety of water sources when constructing clean water facilities. Water sources that are consumed daily are safer from contamination by polluting materials if the water sources are protected, both in terms of construction and distance from sources of pollution such as latrines, rubbish dumps and industrial waste.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank the Dean of the Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, who has provided support to the writing team so that this research can be carried out properly. Furthermore, the team of authors would like to thank all those who have helped until the end of this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

References

- [1] World Health Organization. Diarrhoeal disease [Internet]. 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/health-topics/diarrhoea#tab=tab_1
- [2] Ira. Menengok Perkembangan Diare Di Indonesia [Internet]. MediaKom Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. 2019. Available from: <https://mediakom.kemkes.go.id/2019/08/menengok-perkembangan-diare-di-indonesia/>
- [3] Southeast Sulawesi Central Statistics Agency. Number of disease cases by district, city and type of disease in Southeast Sulawesi. Kendari; 2020.
- [4] Hasan MM, Alam K. Inequality in access to improved drinking water sources and childhood diarrhea in low- and middle-income countries. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2020;226(May):113493.
- [5] Anand A, Roy N. Transitioning toward Sustainable Development Goals: The Role of Household Environment in Influencing Child Health in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia Using Recent Demographic Health Surveys. *Front public Heal* [Internet]. 2016;4. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2016.00087>
- [6] Guo A, Bowling JM, Bartram J, Kayser G. Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Rural Health-Care Facilities: A Cross-Sectional Study in Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, Rwanda, Uganda, and Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* [Internet]. 2017;97(4):1033–42. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.17-0208>
- [7] Chakravarty I, Bhattacharya A, Das SK. Water, sanitation and hygiene: The unfinished agenda in the World Health Organization South-East Asia Region. *WHO South-East Asia J Public Health*. 2017;6(2):22–33.
- [8] Husain Z, Das P. Reducing child diarrhea in India: Shifting policy focus from source of water to quality. *Water Resour Econ*. 2023;42(April).
- [9] Mehta L. Water and Human Development. *World Dev*. 2014;59(July):59–69.

- [10] Rabbani M, Kazemi F. Water need and water use efficiency of two plant species in soil-containing and soilless substrates under green roof conditions. *J Environ Manage* [Internet]. 2021;302(Part A):113950. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113950>
- [11] Ju Y-R, Chen C-F, Chen C-W, Lim YC, Lo W-T, Dong C-D. Concurrent assessment of water parameters and vital-based zooplankton community in an industrial harbor. *Reg Stud Mar Sci*. 2021;46(July):101887.
- [12] Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation of the Minister of Health of Indonesia Number 32 of 2017 concerning Environmental Health Quality Standards and Water Health Requirements for Sanitation Hygiene, Swimming Pools, Aqua Solus and Public Baths. Indonesian Ministry of Health; 2017
- [13] Harsa IMS. The Relationship Between Water Sources and Diarrhea Incidents in Residents of Kampung Baru Ngagelrejo Wonokromo Surabaya. *J Agromedicine Med Sci*. 2019;5(3):124–9.
- [14] Kumar SB, Shinde AH, Mehta R, Bhattacharya A, Haldar S. Simple, one-step dye-based kit for bacterial contamination detection in a range of water sources. *Sensors Actuators B Chem*. 2018;276(December):121–7.
- [15] Marini M, Ofarimawan D, Ambarita LP. The relationship between drinking water sources and the incidence of diarrhea in South Sumatra province. *Means of Dissemination Inf Has Litbang*. 2020;12(1).
- [16] Ifandi S. Relationship between use of latrines and water sources and the incidence of diarrhea among toddlers in Sindue District. *J Public Health*. 2017;2(2).
- [17] Italia I, Kamaluddin H, Sitorus J, Ico J. The Relationship between Hand Washing Habits, Bathing Habits and Water Sources with the Incidence of Diarrhea in Toddlers in the Working Area of Community Health Center 4 Ulu, Seberang Ulu I District, Palembang. *J Medicine and Health*. 2016;3(3).
- [18] Baia CC, Vargas TF, Ribeiro VA, Laureano J de J, Boyer R, Bastos CCD, et al. Microbiological Contamination of Urban Groundwater in the Brazilian Western Amazon. *J Water*. 2022;14(24):4023.
- [19] Jumakil, Kamrin, Rahman, Fithria, Handayani L. The Relationship between Latrine Ownership and the Incidence of Diarrhea in Toddlers in South Buton Regency, 2022. *Int J Curr Sci Res Rev*. 2023;6(4):2649–53.
- [20] Jimmy DH, Sundufu AJ, Malanoski AP, Jacobsen KH, Ansumana R, Leski TA, et al. Water quality is associated with public health risk in Bo, Sierra Leone. *Environ Monit Assess*. 2013;185:241–251.
- [21] Hynds P, Misstear BD, Gill LW, Murphy HM. Groundwater source contamination mechanisms: Physicochemical profile clustering, risk factor analysis and multivariate modeling. *J Contam Hydrol*. 2014;159(April):47–56.
- [22] Rahmanian N, Ali SHB, Homayounfar M, Ali NJ, Rehan M, Sadeh Y, et al. Analysis of Physicochemical Parameters to Evaluate the Drinking Water Quality in the State of Perak, Malaysia. *J Chemistry* [Internet]. 2015;2015:716125. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/716125>
- [23] Odonkor ST, Mahami T. *Escherichia coli* as a Tool for Disease Risk Assessment of Drinking Water Sources. *Int J Microbiol*. 2020;2020.